

THERMOPLASTIC COMPOSITE BEARINGS: TRIBOLOGICAL PROPERTIES AS A FUNCTION OF THE MATERIAL STRUCTURE

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SUMMARY: In the study presented here, thermoplastic filament winding of journal bearings with functional properties over their cross sections was performed by the use of different commingled yarns. The raw material of the sliding surface consisted of PTFE-, aramid-, and polyamide fibers, of which the latter were molten and then transferred into the final matrix of the composite tube element. For this special filament winding process, the processing parameters were optimized, in order to realize a bulk composite structure. The composition of the raw materials and the winding geometry were varied. Thus, the influence of these parameters on the tribological behaviour of the bearing could be determined.

KEYWORDS: Thermoplastic filament winding, thermoplastic composite materials, friction, wear, coefficient of friction, winding parameters, injection molding

INTRODUCTION

Polymeric composites are predestinated for low weight and high stiffness constructions. New developments have also focussed on the use of thermoplastic matrices, because of their advantageous mechanical properties, especially the higher toughness when compared to traditional thermosets. Another advantage of these thermoplastic matrices is that no final curing process in an oven or autoclave is necessary. Therefore, these materials are especially suitable for continuous manufacturing processes such as thermoplastic filament winding [1,2] or pultrusion [3]. Impregnation, consolidation and cooling are performed continuously during the manufacturing process. However, still a major problem in processing of thermoplastic composites is the high viscosity of the matrix material. As a result, processing parameters like temperature, pressure and winding speed have to be optimized properly in order to achieve both, a good fiber distribution and a strong bonding between fibers and matrix [4].

Composite journal bearings are presently manufactured by a thermoset filament winding technology. A better alternative, based on fundamental tribological studies, would be however, to use continuous fiber reinforced thermoplastic composites, because of their superior friction and wear properties. But one problem in using these materials for such purposes is, that special manufacturing processes are required.

THERMOPLASTIC FILAMENT WINDING EQUIPMENT

The possibility of welding continuous fiber reinforced thermoplastics enables the combination of two manufacturing steps, i.e. filament winding and consolidation, in one continuous production process. Filament winding of composite materials with thermoplastic matrices is more complicated than wet winding of thermosetting composites, due to the higher viscosity of thermoplastic polymers. During this process, the incoming yarn has to be melt impregnated and immediately consolidated onto the previously wound surface at the lay down point (nip point). The in situ filament winding device is shown in Figure 1. A two axis motion controller coordinated the mandrel's rotation and the movement of the support to which the tow guidance system was attached. Hence, a predetermined fiber path could be realized. Tow tension was measured and controlled. A defined compaction force was applied by employing a compaction roller, or a temperature controlled sliding shoe.

Figure 1: Thermoplastic filament winding device

The melting of the tow material was realized in the following way: The raw material bobbin was positioned in a prewarming chamber (Fig. 1), which raised the temperature of the tow in front of the preheating zone from room temperature up to about 200°C. In this way, the difference between the raw material temperature and the matrix material's melting temperature was significantly reduced. After leaving the prewarming chamber, the tow passed through a hot air preheating zone. The final heating arrangement occurred in the nip point area, which consisted of two hot air guns, the first one heating the incoming yarn, the second one the previously wound surface. An additional infrared line heater provided a fine tuning of the nip point temperature. The mandrel temperature was also measured and controlled. Measurements of the ring surface temperatures were carried out by two pyrometers. The first one was focused at the nip point, the second one at the incoming surface of the wound part before reaching the hot air zone. In this arrangement, the filament winding parameters were: winding speed (v_w), mandrel temperature (T_M), nip point temperature (T_{NP}), preheating temperature (T_{PH}), prewarming temperature (T_{PW}), consolidation force (F_C), and tow tension (F_T).

RAW MATERIALS FOR FILAMENT WINDING

The first type of yarn used in this study consisted of PTFE-, aramid-, and polyamide fibers, of which the latter were melted and therefore transferred into the final matrix of the composite tube element (Figure 2). The second material investigated was a polymer powder impregnated and with a thin polymer matrix sheath surrounded flexible reinforcing fiber bundle. The particular components consisted of glass fibers and a polyethyleneterephthalate matrix material (GF-PET-1200tex).

Figure 2: Raw materials for thermoplastic filament winding

INJECTION MOLDING EQUIPMENT AND PARAMETERS

In this study a commercially available fully hydraulic injection molding machine (ARBURG ALLROUNDER® 270 V) equipped with a SELOGICA® process control system was used. The most important processing parameters were the temperature of the molten thermoplastic, the mold temperature, the injection pressure, the injection time, the holding pressure and the holding time. Optimum processing parameters for a certain part were not only a function of the thermoplastic used but also a function of the mold geometry. For every commercially available, injection moldable thermoplastic polymer the processing properties are given in a certain range. Starting from this point, the injection parameters were systematically varied and optimized. At first, simple rings with an inner diameter of 40 mm, a width of 20 mm and a wall thickness of 4 mm were injection molded out of PA66, filled with 30 wt % short glass fibers. In the next step a filament wound ring with an inner diameter of 40 mm, a width of 20 mm and a thickness of about 2 mm was placed as an insert into the same mold and then preheated with a hot air gun (400°C) for one minute. Subsequently, it was embedded into a glass fiber reinforced thermoplastic PA66 matrix by injection molding. For this process, also the injection parameters such as mass temperature, tool temperature and injection pressure had to be optimized in order to achieve optimum material properties and strong bonding between insert and injected material.

COMBINATION OF FILAMENT WINDING AND INJECTION MOLDING

Alternatively to the complete manufacturing of the bearings by filament winding, a thinner filament wound bearing layer could be encapsulated by short glass fiber reinforced polyamide, injection molded around the wound insert [5]. Critical processing issues were (1) the control of the adhesion between the composite insert and the surrounding material, and (2) the different thermal expansion conditions of the two partners in contact. The correct design between the two is a basic requirement for dimensional stability of the final component.

Figure 3: Combination of thermoplastic filament winding and injection molding

Injection molding technology allows the production of very complex geometries. The disadvantage is that only short fiber reinforced thermoplastics can be processed, and furthermore, that fiber orientation is highly dependent on the mold geometry and processing parameters. Thermoplastic filament winding, on the other hand, allows the production of continuous fiber reinforced, relatively simple structures such as rings with a defined fiber orientation and a high fiber volume content [1, 2]. The combination of these two technologies permits the fabrication of structural parts with complex geometries and functional properties. During this study, a thermoplastic filament wound ring was used as an insert embedded in a short fiber reinforced thermoplastic component of a different geometry, produced by injection molding (Figure 3).

TESTING OF THE COMPOSITE BEARINGS

Testing of this final component in a journal bearing tester indicated its good performance in terms of low coefficient of friction, low wear and high thermal stability under various pressure, temperature and velocity conditions. A cross section of the inner layer of such a bearing is presented in Figure 4.

Figure 4 : Cross section of the sliding surface of a thermoplastic composite bearing

Using optimized thermoplastic filament winding parameters, the winding angles and the composition of the sliding surface material were varied systematically. The influence of these parameters on the tribological properties of the bearings were investigated using a journal bearing tester. The components indicated a good performance in terms of low coefficient of friction, low wear and high thermal stability, in relation to competitive thermoset bearings under comparable pressure, temperature and velocity conditions. The correlation between winding angle and coefficient of friction is given in Figure 5. This lay down angle of the raw material on the mandrel was varied between 0° (hoop winding) and 30° . In the range between 0° and 7° , the coefficient of friction is nearly constant at a value of about 0,085. A further increase of the winding angle led to friction coefficients of 0,16.

Figure 5: Coefficient of friction of filament wound thermoplastic composite bearings depending on the winding angle

Figure 7: Coefficient of friction of filament wound thermoplastic composite bearings depending on the PTFE weight content

In further experiments, the composition of the composite material was varied. The weight content of PTFE was altered between 0 and 14%. The results can be seen in Figure 7. An increase of PTFE weight content resulted in lower coefficients of friction. In fact, the best coefficient of friction of 0.085 was measured with a PTFE content of 14% and a winding angle of 0°.

RESULTS OF INJECTION MOLDING EXPERIMENTS

The results of the injection molding experiments are given in Figure 8 and 9. In these experiments the filament wound sliding surface was used as an insert and the outer structure was injection molded around it. A preheating of the insert using hot air of 400°C was necessary to guarantee a strong bonding between insert and surrounding polymer. This bonding was determined using a special shear test [6]. The influence of the polymer's mass temperature during injection molding on the interlaminar shear strength between insert and polymer is shown in Figure 8. The mass temperature was varied between 260°C and 340°C. An increase of mass temperature up to 300°C resulted in shear strength values of 18 MPa. A further increase could not improve the bonding.

Figure 8: Interlaminar shear strength between insert and injected material as a function of mass temperature

The correlation between tool temperature and shear strength is given in Figure 9. During these experiments the tool temperature was varied between 20°C and 120°C. Here, an increase of temperature resulted in higher shear values. The highest tool temperature of 120°C let to shear values of about 20 MPa.

Figure 9 : Interlaminar shear strength between insert and injected material as a function of tool temperature

CONCLUSIONS

The manufacturing of a new type of bearing using thermoplastic matrix composites processed by filament winding, optionally in combination with injection molding, led to the following results: (a) Aramid fibers provided high strength and PTFE fibers, both embedded in a PA66 matrix, resulted in a low coefficient of friction of the bearings. The best results could be obtained with a PTFE weight content of 14 % and a winding angle of 0° (hoop winding). (b) During injection molding, preheating of insert rings resulted in much better adhesion to the injection molded outer part. For the materials investigated (PA66), a mass temperature of 300°C in combination with a tool temperature of 120 °C resulted in the best adhesion between insert and surrounding polymer. (c) Further work needs to be done in order to optimize the bearings by the use of a finer commingling quality of yarn, the adjustment of optimum fiber orientation angles in the sliding surface and other fiber matrix material combinations.

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